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LOOKING THROUGH THE LANGUAGE REGISTER AND ITS INFLUENCE

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When I was a child, I usually hear the word, "American dream". It stuck in my mind and as I grow older, I asked people that surround me about the words they uttered long time ago. And the answer was they wanted to go to America and upon hearing these lines, I personally wanted to go to also. America has influenced a lot in many ways like music, fashion and even the way they talk specifically the vulgar and slang words and their facial expressions per say to the Asian countries most specifically the Philippines and of course other neighboring countries. In the Philippines, our educational system adopted the American educational system since Americans has greatly influenced our system. Filipino educators even idolized American speakers and writers and even we speak the language more than our own language.

Language register is the level of formality with which you speak. Different situations and people call for different registers (Nordquist, 2018). This register is conversational in tone. It is the language used among and between friends. Words are general, rather than technical. This register may include more slang and colloquialisms. The study entitled, "THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN AMERICAN POPULAR CULTURE ON THE ENGLISH VOCABULARY by Bojan Kašuba (2016) sought to describe modern American popular culture and its influence on the English language, specifically on the vocabulary. Furthermore, the thesis deals with morphology, primarily word-formation. Basic linguistic terms such as morphemes, words, lexemes, and affixes are explained. Additionally, a brief comparison between first language vocabulary acquisition and foreign language vocabulary acquisition is presented.

The examination of specific art forms or artefacts names such as films, TV series, music, technology, social media, politics, and fashion provided the core of the popular culture analysis American popular culture as multi-faceted as being described in the reading material. American popular culture is multi-faceted, but it is also molded with duality. It is low form, but it can also represent high form and a representation of trash culture, but it can also be admired for its diversity and colorfulness. Language and society each represent one side of the same coin. Indeed, American films, TV series and pop songs can change society, they can also change language.

For example, the noun truthiness, was used in a segment in The Colbert Report to elicit humor, but has outgrown its original purpose, as it is used as a mockery of political and journalistic speech for bending the truth to suit one's purpose. Furthermore, words' characteristics are important in vocabulary acquisition, but they are not the only deciding factor in making them a part of a person's mental lexicon.

With all these descriptions mentioned above, indeed, native, and non-native speakers tend to acquire new vocabulary from American pop culture incidentally thru different media platforms and very good avenues for future research as well for new word discoveries.

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